

Finlay Allan

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MASCULINITIES, MALE IDENTITY AND NATIONHOOD: THE COMPLEX
REPRESENTATION IN RONA MUNRO'S *THE JAMES PLAYS*

Primary Supervisor: Sofia Nakou

Secondary Supervisor: Steve Collins

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Abstract

A month before the Scottish electorate voted in the 2014 Independence Referendum, Rona Munro's *The James Plays* made its debut. The trilogy is comprised of instalments dedicated to James I, II and III, exploring these Scottish kings' reigns. At a time where Scotland was undergoing a divisive debate on the future of governance and perceptions of Scottish nationality, Munro's narratives of medieval monarchs interrogate the nature of identity and nationhood. This research paper specifically focuses on how the depiction of the Jameses serves to critique the nature of masculinity, male identity and nationhood in contemporary Scotland. This is contextualised within the nation's post-war theatre culture, considering Munro's writing alongside other work that engages with Scottish identity, as well as examining her contribution to the representation of Scottish masculinity. The intersectional frameworks of masculinity studies, hegemonic masculinity theory, feminist theory and gender studies are applied as lenses to a textual analysis. By utilising this method and methodology, the subversive masculinities of the three Jameses is examined in relation to the hegemonic masculine ideals of the patriarchal structures they inhabit. In particular, how hegemonic masculinity defines leadership and power, how it influences the personal and private lifestyles of the Jameses, as well as how *The James Plays* challenge hegemonic masculine ideals. Through this targeted analysis, Munro's representation of the complexity of masculinity, male identity and nationhood in contemporary Scotland is outlined, demonstrating how these attributes influence and conflict with one another.

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This is the culmination of my years of study at the University of the West of Scotland. I simply would not have achieved this without my time with the Performance faculty. Alongside the named above, thanks to (in no particular order): James Layton, Catriona Fallow, Henry Bell, Eve Katsouraki, Stephen Langston, Jane Robertson and Jo Ronan.

I will take this opportunity to share my enthusiasm for Rona Munro and her writing. There is always a concern that, in dissecting a text, appreciation in reading it beyond an academic context will diminish. *The James Plays* continue to intrigue and excite me, even without a desire to find a citation for a chapter. Beyond her contribution to Scottish theatre, Munro is the only person to have written for the classic and new series of Doctor Who; a remarkable triumph. Should the play cycle continue onto James VI, and the production is in need of an emerging actor with an acute familiarity of this writing, I can only hope she'll happen upon my portfolio at www.finlayallan.co.uk. My CV and contact details are available there.

Praise to my siblings for being so humble despite how brilliant a brother they have.

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Ethics and Plagiarism

Ethical Considerations

This study did not involve the use of Human Participants in the collection of data. There was, therefore, no application made for ethical approval to the Module Coordinator.

Plagiarism Statement

I confirm that by signing, dating and submitting this project, I have read, understood and accepted the University's regulations in relation to Cheating and Plagiarism.

Signed Finlay Allan
Name FINLAY ALLAN
Date 12/08/2025

Chapter 1. Introduction

The James Plays are a part of the only history play cycle in contemporary Scottish theatre. As a trilogy, they explore themes of power, authority, nationhood, family, and gender dynamics. One of the key aspects of the plays is the way in which the interplay between masculinity and power is represented across the trilogy. The kings are three unique men, historically and in terms of representation. They are shaped and moulded in differing ways by the demands of their status and the role masculine identity plays in their immediate relationships. In this dissertation, I explore how Rona Munro examines the interplay between masculinity, male identity, leadership and power.

This study focuses on the three Jameses, evaluating Munro's fictionalisation of the monarchs in relation to hegemonic masculinity. Connell and Messerschmidt define hegemonic masculinity

as the pattern of practice (i.e., things done, not just a set of role expectations or an identity) that allowed men's dominance over women to continue.

Hegemonic masculinity was distinguished from other masculinities, especially subordinated masculinities. Hegemonic masculinity was not assumed to be normal in the statistical sense; only a minority of men might enact it. But it was certainly normative. It embodied the currently most honored way of being a man, it required all other men to position themselves in relation to it, and it ideologically legitimated the global subordination of women to men.

(2005, p. 832)

These '[d]ominant constructions of masculinity dictate, to a large extent, that men should be unemotional, logical, independent, hard but fair, benevolent but not vulnerable, physically strong, heterosexual, sexually dominant and so on' (O'Leary, 1998 quoted in Seymour, 2003, p. 37). Whitehead explains that hegemonic masculinity is further defined by being 'competitive, combative, calculative, focused on self and the control of others' (1999, p. 58). In *The James Plays*, Munro critiques the role of masculinity and hegemonic structures in contemporary culture and society. As characters, the Jameses are portrayed at the forefront of the political and social systems of Scotland, where the dominance of hegemonic masculinity in these areas is demonstrated and interrogated. Consequently, 'the attention inevitably shifts from 'men' as a dominant, oppressive gender category, on to masculinity as a dominant gender ideology' (Whitehead, 1999, p. 59). The Jameses are a dual

interrogation of Scottish masculine identity and the role of masculinity in leadership and nationhood.

It is suggested by L. Munro that the use of the past

can be historical, mythical or fictional; it may be a site of memory, subjectivity or nostalgia; it can be dynastic or popular in its concerns; the past may even turn out to be simultaneously the present, or even the future.

(2011, p. 105)

Through medieval Scotland, Munro reflects the contemporary Scotland of 2014, gripped in a divisive referendum on independence. Theatre critic Michael Billington (2014) concurs with this assessment, believing the plays serve a dual purpose in depicting a period of Scottish history as well as being 'full of topical resonance' (non-paginated). Rona Munro explores the identities that make up Scotland, presenting alternative narratives that interweave and conflict with the experiences and views of Scottish audiences. It is stated on several occasions throughout the trilogy that the Jameses serve as representatives of both the Scottish people and the nation herself. The exploration of how personal masculine identity functions within their culture is a conduit of attitudes to and perceptions of masculinity in contemporary Scotland.

James I, II and III all embody and present subversive masculine traits and masculinities. Their masculine identity standing in contrast with the hegemonic masculine values of the leadership structure is at the heart of Munro's critique. James I is seen to have a more level-headed approach to negotiations and diplomacy than his contemporaries, as well as an explicit love and respect for his wife and Queen, Joan. James II struggles with fear and insecurity as he endeavours to manage his role as King. James III is a queer man in a culture that does not accommodate queer identity. Through the three Jameses and their positioning in hegemonic structures, Munro explores competing Scottish identities and values, capturing the national debate on what sort of nation Scotland was and could be.

In a culture that has a 'tendency towards patriarchy and the phallogentric' (Scullion, 2000, p. 94), *The James Plays* are notable for their interrogation of patriarchal systems. Munro presents three men who do not fully conform to hegemonic masculine ideals in their innate character, but are pressured to do so through social

expectations and necessity – both in their private lives and their role as a public figure. In Scottish theatre,

the dominance of [...] masculinist constructions of the nation has been challenged in recent decades, not least by contemporary theatre practitioners who have given voice to marginalised sections of the community and highlighted the distance of real men from dominant notions of hegemonic masculinity.

(Reid, 2013, p. 19)

The James Plays is part of a wider movement that endeavours to diversify and authenticate the representation of Scottish men. Munro's trilogy is of particular relevance in this. Not only has she depicted alternative forms of masculinity, she also demonstrates how they are valued and mediated by the dominant hegemonic masculinity of social and cultural values. The king, as a cipher of the people, represents a progression of societal attitudes stagnating against strict hegemonic structures.

The media, as suggested by Brooks and Hérbert (2006), is a component of patriarchal systems and so will facilitate and promote narratives of masculine archetypes. Acknowledging the 'dysfunctional urban male who plays such a significant part in recent Scottish fiction' (Whyte, 1998, p. 274) outlines a representation that Munro writes in relation to as a Scottish playwright. Stevenson argues that 'by the end of the 1970s there was also widespread confidence in the present and future of Scottish theatre' (2019, p. 9). Indeed, Brown believes '[i]t is becoming a cliché to observe that there has been a renaissance in Scottish theatre since the 1970s' (2007, quoted in Brown, 2012, p. 95). However, the 1970s itself 'has been characterised and criticised as rather introspective, urban and quintessentially macho' (Scullion, no date, non-paginated). Due to this, Scottish theatre's exploration of Scottish male identity honed in on a particular form of masculinity.

Reynolds (2006) argues that, during the 1970s, Scottish culture 'was dominated not only by men but also by certain ideas of masculinity and virility' (p. 170). *The Hard Man* (1977) by Tom McGrath and Jimmy Boyle exemplifies this representation of masculinity. It shows 'how a man can be a respected success in a disenfranchised underclass' (Fisher, 2011). The play 'charts Johnny Byrne's Glasgow life from a boyhood of petty crime to brutality, murder, and 'hard man' status in adulthood' (NLS,

2011). This production 'represented a popular depiction of 'Clydeside-ism', albeit with some dangerous edges to their nostalgia' (Scullion, no date). 'Clydesidism constructs the myth of an "authentic", masculine, working class urban life' Caughie (1990, quoted in Martin-Jones, 2009, p. 105) explains. Clydesideism is by no means indicative of the representation of Scottish masculinity in theatre. Indeed, it is not the sole depiction of masculine identity of the 1970s, with John Byrne's play *The Slab Boys* (1978) deviating from 'the masculine urbanity of Clydesideism' (Elliott, 2018, p. 109). Clydesideism is of note is because it is from a period that precipitated Munro's contributions to Scottish playwrighting. Understanding prominent forms of Scottish male representation in theatre offers clarity on the extent to which *The James Plays* adheres to and deviates from conventions.

The James Plays do not shy away from representations of Scottish masculinity that are critiqued for being 'emotionally immature, quick to take offence and to resort to violence' (Petrie, 2014, p. 231). 'Munro represents the Scottish nobles as thuggish, speaking a vulgarized demotic' (Brown, 2016, p. 207). The ruling class of the nation are represented as 'uniquely rough, violent and ungovernable' (McMillan, 2016, p. 383). Through the courts of the three kings, Munro depicts the hegemony of the Hard Man archetype often seen within Scottish theatre. At the same time, she also represents deviations from this hegemonic masculinity. Between the nobles and the Jameses, different expressions of masculine identity are seen in opposition to one another. This portrays the conflicting views of Scottish masculinity that have evolved over the years and were present in the contemporary nation the plays were staged in.

As a trilogy, *The James Plays* spans a tight period of 15th century Scottish history, with the three Jameses being a direct lineage. Whilst the plays stand as their own piece of work, some aspects – such as characters and the consequences of certain events – carry through from one play to the next. Munro explains that 'each play stands alone, an audience doesn't need to have seen the previous instalments, but there are easter eggs and rewards for those who have' (2022, p. 11). In this research project, studying the trilogy as a whole is a deliberate choice. They were written at the same time in response to the same political and cultural event. In each instalment, the Jameses face a constitutional crisis in their respective leaderships,

mirroring the constitutional debate occurring in the Scotland of 2014. The politics of the historical courts and royal household offer perspectives and interpretations on contemporary matters.

The three questions that guide the analysis of *The James Plays* are:

1. To what extent do hegemonic masculine ideals define leadership and power in *The James Plays*?
2. In what ways are hegemonic masculine ideals shown to filter into personal and private lifestyles?
3. In what ways does the play cycle challenge hegemonic masculine values?

Connell and Messerschmidt state that there are 'three 'levels' of hegemony: local ('immediate communities'); regional ('the culture of the nation state'); and global ('transnational arenas')' (2005, quoted in Lomas, 2013, p. 175). These differentiations highlight that masculinity is subject to change, depending on the circumstances in which it is present. This argument has substantially guided the research questions the text is being studied against. The Jameses' status as king pertains to the transnational context, as they represent Scotland in conflict and negotiations; England being a recurring feature of this in the trilogy. They are national leaders, where they are defined by how they respond to the demands and expectations of their court. In a local context, the trilogy presents the romantic, platonic and familial relationships of the Jameses. By considering these three levels, the trilogy's representation of Scottish masculinity in hegemonic structures is explored to a greater extent.

James I: The Key Will Keep the Lock follows James I as he returns to Scotland after a lifetime of imprisonment in England. On condition of his release, he is made to marry the English King Henry's cousin, Joan. When back in his home nation, James finds himself undermined and plotted against by his own Stewart family. James I's imprisonment emasculates him in the eyes of his court, much like his interests in poetry and his prioritisation of diplomacy over ruthlessness. A constitutional crisis is posed by England through the threat of invasion and the implementation of an English Queen on the Scottish throne. Establishing his authority is contingent on the lengths to which he instils and demonstrates hegemonic masculine traits in retaliation to his family. When considered in relation to the 2014 independence

referendum, *James I* exemplifies how nationality and politics are informed by hegemonic masculine ideals. Amongst the court, how James I, as Scotland's leader, can defy England is contingent on how he presents himself as a man.

In *James II: Day of the Innocents*, James II is shown in the grips of a nightmare, reliving the aftermath of his father's death in conflict. Thrust into the position of king, James II strives to pursue a childhood alongside his friend William. James is manipulated by Balvenie and the rest of the Scottish court, who are all in pursuit of their own agendas. After witnessing the slaughter of his cousins, Young Douglas and Davey, James II is shown to be overwhelmed by the violence that surrounds his power. As an adult, James continues to mitigate tensions in his court, unaware of Balvenie's continued manipulation and plotting. This instalment of the trilogy focuses on a constitutional crisis in an internal context. There is little reference to Scotland in relation to England. Instead, it is the immediate, competitive politics of the Scottish court that studies the influence of hegemonic masculinity on power and how this informs the presentation of masculinities in relation to authority.

James III: The True Mirror follows an aggressive and domineering James III, paranoid that his brother, Sandy, is plotting against him. James's wife, Margaret, also stands in frequent opposition to the king and his unpredictable actions. The royal family unit splits in two after Sandy is arrested, accused of treason by James III. James and Margaret and their two sons part ways, Ross following his father and Jamie his mother. Despite the political stakes of the narrative, the concluding instalment of the *James* trilogy focuses on identity in a much more personal context. James III becomes increasingly despondent to his role as king as the play progresses, with Margaret progressively assuming a leadership position. There is a constitutional crisis through an unstable royal family unit and an absent leader for the Scottish nation. Matters of the state runs as an undercurrent in interactions throughout *James III*, with the nature of relationships and individual dynamics being at the forefront. The focus rests on a familial conflict, rather than a political one. As such, the adherence to hegemonic masculinity in the presentation of James III's masculinity critiques how one responds to social expectations on a subjective level, rather than how social expectations inform masculine identities in a wider context.

In this research project, I contextualise Rona Munro's *The James Plays* within the wider Scottish theatre culture. The function of the history play genre in commenting on contemporary matters is examined. Thereafter, the 2014 Scottish Independence Referendum period is discussed in further detail, outlining the political climate that the plays were written in response to. The reading that supports this study is examined in a literature review, with the method and methodology explained thereafter. In this, the insight offered by a textual analysis is detailed, as well as how the intersectional frameworks of masculine studies, feminist theory and gender studies guide an understanding of Munro's work. The findings of the textual analysis through these lenses are presented, offering a perspective in response to the three research questions. Chapters 5, 6 and 7 focus on two specific instances in the overall trilogy each, discussing them in detail before they are reviewed in the conclusion. At this point, the research questions are considered alongside one another, giving an overview of Munro's complex representation of masculinity, male identity and nationhood in *The James Plays*.

Chapter 2. Research Context

To place Rona Munro within the context of Scotland's playwrighting culture, the establishment of the modern Scottish theatre culture must be explained. By outlining this, her contribution to playwrighting that engages with national identity is argued in a wider landscape. Thereafter, the history play genre will be studied in order to understand how it serves to commentate on contemporary matters, such as 21st century Scottish male identity. Then, the impact of the 2014 Scottish political climate on the writing of the plays is engaged with.

Brown (2019, non-paginated) suggests that 'Scotland is unusual, if not necessarily unique, in being a nation whose finest dramatists are, arguably, alive and working today', placing Rona Munro and her contemporaries at the forefront of the nation's theatre culture. Smith (1998) states that there has been a 're-emergence of a Scottish theatre profession since the Second World War' (p. 307). Brown concurs with this assessment, saying that the post-war era is when Scottish theatre 'sparks into life'. Such a progression of the nation's theatre culture is not an isolated incident; it is concurrent with an evolution of Scottish identity in a wider context.

Scullion explains that

the reappraisal of Scottishness in terms of sociology, political theory, and representation in the media was, by the mid-1980s, reasonably developed. However, and despite the impact of 7:84, the success of new writing initiatives at the Royal Lyceum Theatre and the Traverse Theatre in Edinburgh, and the new internationalism of the Citizens' Theatre in Glasgow, a diverse and rigorous understanding of Scotland and theatre was really only beginning at that time, and consequently it has taken rather longer to develop to some degree of maturity.

(2002, p. 251)

In many areas, Scottish identity was being evaluated and better understood. In turn, so too was Scottish theatre engaging with questions of national identity. Brown, Ramage and Horvat explain:

The vitality of contemporary Scottish theatre can be seen to be a key expression, and now arguably a determinant, of national cultural identity, or to be more precise, identities, male and female, both beyond and within the Central Belt, heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual, and transsexual, Scots, English and Gaelic language based. [...] What is more the cultural identities expressed are more and more clearly based on a modern international world-view which sees Scottish themes and concerns as part and parcel of, and engaged in creative interaction with, the international stage and human experience world-wide.

(2000, p. 25)

Scottish theatre was presenting narratives from across Scotland, expanding on the varying languages, genders and sexualities of the Scottish population. In this, it was understood that Scottish nationality was itself comprised of a multiplicity of identities, placed within a wider, global context. It is within this context that Munro's *The James Plays* sits. With the independence referendum establishing itself as a period of discourse in contemporary Scotland, *The James Plays* depicts a nation gripped by tumultuous political events. Through monarchs and nobles from centuries ago, Munro highlights how identities are informed by and respond to their social and cultural context.

Perceptions of Scottish identity are noted for being built on an understanding of Scotland's past. This engagement with the nation's history is argued to have a detrimental impact on a present understanding of identity. Reid (2013) finds

a consensus of sorts exists about the roots of Scots' predilection for highly selective and sentimentalised accounts of their own history. Since the Treaty of the Union in 1707, this argument goes, Scotland has lacked real political agency and has turned instead to over-inscribed historical narratives for a sense of cultural identity. Moreover, Scottish culture has become distorted and stunted in the process.

(pp. 6-7)

Implied here is that Scotland is culturally stuck in the past. Indeed, that Scottish identity has been restricted by the nation's union with England. This is a historical event being used to inform a political argument. 'The quest for truth is less important than the harnessing of interpretations of history to political ends,' argues Kearton (2005, p. 26). Pairing this with Reid's (2013) outlined argument above, Scotland and England forming a Union in 1707 is being interpreted to present a nationalist argument for why a Scottish cultural identity has been curtailed in the present. Applying this to the historical narratives of Munro's trilogy, *The James Plays*' use of history serves a particular function beyond historical narrative. This period of Scottish history is engaged with in service of examining 21st century Scotland. In this research project, the focus is on how the trilogy depicts Scottish male identities and the way hegemonic masculine identity is infused into negotiations of power. Despite the medieval setting, this study of the three James monarchs is a response to contemporary notions of masculinities in Scotland.

Analysing Scotland through her history is argued by Wormald (1985) to have a negative impact on the understanding of the nation's past. It is suggested that an interest in Scotland's history 'is sustained mainly by a diet of myth, legend, and rubbish' (1985, p. 768). From this critical perspective, *The James Plays* contributes to this, pursuing analysis of 21st century Scotland at the expense of learning more of 15th century Scotland. Munro (2016) is candid about taking liberties with historical fact in the interest of the narratives. But Reid argues that Scotland's history has been 'circulated, distorted, sentimentalized and mythologized in a process of representational overload that until quite recently risked replacing meaningful focus on the present' (2017, p. 89). Considering the trilogy in this context suggests that they contribute to a bastardization of Scotland's past, ignoring the truth in favour of storytelling. Additionally, this focus on the past does not serve an understanding of the contemporary landscape, but instead fixates on ideations of what came before. But this negates the dual purpose of history plays, in that they serve to depict the past whilst also speaking to the period they were written in. Munro writes of medieval Scotland in her trilogy, but she is writing for the Scotland of 2014.

Reicher, Hopkins and Harrison state that historical events and figures informing contemporary understandings of identity is not especial to Scotland. Further to this, the symbols of Scottish identity – Bruce, Bannockburn, Burns and others – are all safely dead and hence open to unlimited use. The king and the battle can be made to entrench either Scottish independence or rugged self-sufficiency. The poet can be quoted to make the Scots lovers of state socialism or haters of state bureaucracy. We have as many pasts as we have futures. (2009, p. 32)

History is not a conclusive understanding of identity; it is used to inform interpretations of it. Argued above is that figures and events of the past can be used to develop opinions in the present on what should happen in the future. On the pertinence of the past in the contemporary world, Munro (2022) argues:

History is the foundation that forms our present, I think popular culture can do a really important job, examining and revealing the nature of the ground on which we now stand. (p. 11)

The James Plays trilogy presents an independent Scottish kingdom, navigating conflicting perceptions on how the nation should be led. At the time of writing, Scotland was in the midst of a national debate on whether to progress within or

outwith the United Kingdom. There was a particular focus on the nature of leadership for Scotland and how the Scottish electorate wished to be governed. This historical period of fraught political systems is symbolic of the uncertainty facing Scotland's political future. The tension and debates between figures that run throughout the trilogy are reminiscent of the matters being thoroughly discussed in 21st century Scotland, in both the political and public sphere.

Historical fact is not adhered to in *The James Plays*. Munro herself is keen to note 'that some small liberties have been taken with known events in order to serve our stories' (2016, p. vii). Brown (2016) assumes a critical stance on the use of historical fact in her trilogy, finding Munro to have 'a more cavalier approach to historical accuracy' (p. 206) compared to a prior work of hers, *The Last Witch* (2009). But this criticism evaluates the trilogy as a documentation of historical record, which it is not. Billington finds it 'somewhat perverse to argue that a history play dealt with the past' (2009, p. 390), stating that it is 'a genre that brings a speculative imagination to recorded events' (p. 390). In Scottish theatre, there is a precedent for the genre being used to analyse the present.

History plays such as Stewart Conn's *The Burning* (Royal Lyceum, Edinburgh, 1971), Hector MacMillan's *The Rising* (Dundee Rep, 1973) and Donald Campbell's *The Jesuit* (Traverse, Edinburgh), 1976) utilised historical material with the express aim of holding up a mirror to contemporary Scotland.

(Reid, 2013, p. 10)

The James Plays continue this trend, using historical figures and events to reflect 21st century matters. They are contemporary plays written for contemporary audience. As such, the historical narratives are not the focal point; they are a tool to explore familiar topics from a different perspective.

On the writing of *The James Plays*, Munro explains: 'My desire to write a history cycle focusing on the medieval kings and queens of Scotland arose when I first saw the Royal Shakespeare Company stage the entire cycle of Shakespeare's history plays over three days' (2022, p. 11). She found that Shakespeare's plays were instrumental in creating a general awareness of historical figures and periods for audiences. However, delving into Scotland's past is not done in a celebratory way. The trilogy does not use history to embolden and glorify leaders and power structures in Scotland. History acts as a perspective to observe and critique

hegemonic structures in contemporary Scotland. In *The James Plays*, she is critical of contemporary understandings of masculinities, leadership and authority in Scotland.

The history play genre has been used by other Scottish playwrights to engage with contemporary matters. Much like Munro has done with her play cycle, Liz Lochhead utilises historical events for commentary on present day issues (Rodríguez González, 2008). Like the individual instalments of *The James Plays*, Lochhead's *Mary Queen of Scots Got Her Head Chopped Off* (1987) focuses on a historical Scottish monarch's identity in a position of power. In representing the character's personal identity, the wider system of leadership and authority they are a part of is also observed. Making Mary the focal point of a narrative is a notable departure from convention, as the

average historical drama is a male-centred affair. That's why Liz Lochhead's 1987 classic stands out. It isn't merely that, in *Mary and Elizabeth*, she fields two regal women protagonists [...] it is that she sets loose a distinctively female sensibility on this tragedy about the rival queens of Scotland and England.

(Fisher, 2009)

Through historical fact, Lochhead is applying contemporary values of gender roles to her characters, detailing 'the problematics of being a queen and woman in a time which supported the myth of patriarchy' (Ahmetpahić, 2022, p. 233). *Mary Queen of Scots* depicts 'a denigration of feminine virtues and emulation of masculine ones for performing the duty of a monarch' (p. 234). This accentuates the focus of *The James Plays* on the three kings. Where Lochhead is exploring the necessity for women to adopt masculine traits in leadership, Munro depicts how perceptions of authority influence subversive masculinities. Through the history genre, both playwrights are critiquing contemporary values and structures that facilitate hegemonic views of gender identities and roles.

Gish (2013) notes that Lochhead's work is renowned for the infusion of feminism and diversity into the storytelling. Comparatively, Munro (quoted in McMillan, 2022, non-paginated) explains: 'As a playwright, I'm always interested in groups whose voices we've not heard before, or not heard enough'. Through their playwrighting, Munro and Lochhead alike give a platform to marginalised voices. In Lochhead's *Mary Queen of Scots Got Her Head Chopped Off*, it is a female narrative followed in a

position of authority. In Munro's trilogy, gender roles are explored in the portrayal of subversive masculinities in positions of authority. In her writing, Liz Lochhead endeavours to remove 'the sense of nationalism from monolithic and masculine definitions' (Gölcük Mirza, 2023, p. 35). In *The James Plays*, Munro instead engages directly with the relationship between nationalism and masculinity. Across the trilogy, parallels are drawn between the debates of the court and the progression of the Scottish nationalist movement. Nationalism acts as another lens that Scottish masculinities are analysed through.

Scullion (no date) insists that 'Rona Munro's trilogy of *The James Plays* caught a moment of cultural, social and political debate and celebration of the independence referendum'. It was a seismic period in Scotland, with Law (2015) explaining:

In the six months leading up to the referendum vote on 18 September 2014 Scotland experienced a period of exceptionally heightened political discourse, a widespread form of political participation unusual in western liberal democracies. For almost two years fundamental questions about nation, state and society that are routinely taken for granted were exposed to widespread public discussion and debate involving millions of individuals normally silenced by the political fetish.

(p. 3)

The unprecedented engagement of the Scottish public with the political sphere prompted a debate not only of the economic possibilities of the nation, but also with fundamental questions on what sort of nation she was and could be. Notions of Scottish identity underpinned this. Reicher, Hopkins and Harrison explain that many were persuaded in their vote 'upon the ability to follow a Scottish way of life – that is to say, one based on Scottish values and beliefs' (2009, p. 32). *The James Plays* were, as described by Ferguson (2014, non-paginated), 'part of a six-month National Theatre of Scotland season exploring Scottish identity'. They are a direct response to the exploration of national identity that had developed in conjunction with the debate on Scottish independence.

Attitudes to Scottish independence are explored within the drama of *The James Plays* through the relationship of masculinity and nationalism. Within the context of the plays and the period, it is wise not to conflate Scottish national identity with Scottish nationalism. Nationalism is a form of Scottish identity, but Scottish

nationality comprises many different political persuasions. Kearton explains in more detail:

A conceptual distinction is made between Scottish national identity and Scottish nationalism as two separate, although interrelated, phenomena. [...] A distinct Scottish national identity survived within (although not unchanged by) the Union, in part due to the continuation of a distinct Scottish civil society after 1707. Dual identities were (and are) possible. Related to this, national identity is not the preserve of anyone political party. [...] Consequently, the relationship between electoral support, national identity and preferred constitutional outcome is highly complex.

(2005, p. 24)

The complexity that Kearton notes was developed further by the referendum debate.

Alongside its relationship to national identity exists

a distinction between two kinds of nationalism: the good kind, which allows national emotions to correspond with abstract moral principles, and the bad kind, which leaves no room for rational discourse, representing an irrational relic or retrogressive return to a barbarous past. The former is commonly associated with civic nationalism, the latter with nationalism's more ethnic forms.

(Tamir, 2019, pp. 424-425)

Ethnic nationalism is explored in the plays through the anti-English, pro-Scottish attitudes of members of the Scottish courts. This stands in contra to civic nationalism's 'inclusive, forward-looking vision of the nation' (Kearton, 2005, p. 25) that was at the forefront of the pro-independence campaign. Through the courts of the James monarchs, Munro reflects the differing values of nationalism through their relationship to Scottish masculinity.

The late 20th century saw a left-wing populist push that advocated for independence. The movement sought to build a link 'between Scotland's multiple masculinities, and the way in which they could be combined to articulate a national hegemonic masculinity as a countervailing, defensive bulwark against the disembedding of the economy from society by London planners and multi-national corporations' (Gibbs and Scothorne, 2020, p. 237). Within this nationalist movement, hegemonic masculine ideals were pursued to defend against perceived exploitations of Scotland. Hegemonic masculine traits were seen as a means to assert control and authority over external forces. The Scottish courts of *The James Plays* reflect this ideal of 'a clearly gendered hierarchy of heroic Scottish workers and ruling-class English villains' (Gibbs and Scothorne, 2020, pp. 237-238). The Scottish nobles of

each instalment rally around figures who defend Scotland against any and all forms of English aggression. James I establishes his leadership through a nationalistic speech against England, decrying their targeting of Scottish wealth. This sentiment is continued into the second instalment, where Davey celebrates his brother, Young Douglas, in asking the court: 'Who holds the border?' (Munro, 2016, p. 122); 'Who keeps Scotland?' (p. 122); 'Who stops the English?' (p. 122). In response, the nobles shout Douglas's name. Here, Young Douglas' leadership is valued in fighting for Scotland's independence against the neighbouring Kingdom. James III shows resentment that his reign is contingent on mediating the threat of an English invasion. Across the trilogy, the leadership of Scotland is intertwined with the antagonization of England. As Scotland's union with England was subject to debate, Munro utilises the two nations' long and complex relationship to draw attention to how presentations of masculinity will be affected by political attitudes and forms of national identity.

In reference to *The James Plays*, McMillan (2016) states:

[...] Scotland, it seems, is a nation still willing to see itself mainly through the eyes of contemptuous others; and for all its ambition, and the sheer brilliance of its staging, the *James* trilogy never achieves the levels of vision and coherence that might change all that.

(p. 383)

This is a critical view of Munro's writing, believing it leans heavily into stereotypes that hinder an authentic portrayal of Scottish identity. It goes as far as to suggest it as reason for the likelihood of the vote going against independence. Billington (2014) gave quite a different review from McMillan, praising Munro for being 'too good a writer to be simply providing seven and a half hours of nationalist propaganda' (non-paginated). It is interesting that these two perspectives offer a positive and negative opinion on the lack of nationalism in the writing; one seeming disheartened, the other enthused. But the matter of independence and Scotland's relationship with England is not ignored by Munro. Sindic and Reicher suggest 'there is solid evidence that high levels of national (Scottish) identification are typical of Scots in general as a minority nation compared to their English neighbours' (2009, p. 125). In the contemporary day, Scottish nationality is defined by many in relation to England. With the trilogy examining Scottish identity at a time of heightened focus on the nation's union with England, it would be shortsighted to ignore how these

attitudes inform identity in Scotland. In *The James Plays*, the three kings lead an independent Scottish kingdom. James I, II and III each hold a particular view in how the nation should move forward, with English relations being a recurrent issue. *The James Plays* reflects the challenges in negotiating the future of Scotland in uncertain times, with a complex international relationship underlying the discussion.

Overall, the politics of the trilogy are framed through the personal stakes for the characters. Brown suggests:

the domestication of the drama [...] marks a dramaturgical trajectory over the trilogy in which the emphasis moves from primary concern with larger political issues, however expressed through family feuding, to a growing, though never absolute, emphasis on power relationships in the domestic sphere, seen in some feminist theory as seat of feminine authority.

(2016, p. 210)

Whilst prescribing domesticity as a centre feminine authority is a derivative gendering of social spaces, it can be reframed in the context of this research. Instead of being defined as a feminine space, instead it is considered against the imposed masculinity of the political sphere. Already, it has been discussed how hegemonic masculine traits will be exhibited in leadership. In the play trilogy, the leading monarch is predominantly male. The only exception to this is Queen Margaret assuming control of the court when James III abandons the position, but even this is a short-lived instance that is demonstrated to be unorthodox (Munro, 2016). In the narrative of the trilogy, the political sphere is seen to be male-dominated. As is argued in this research, negotiations of leadership and power are defined in accordance to hegemonic masculine ideals.

Where women are inferior to men politically, the interaction between male and female characters in a domestic context is telling of their personal attitudes and values. How the Jameses value and treat the women in their lives is also revealing of their subversive masculinities and male identities than their conduct in a position dictated by hegemonic values. The familial aspects feature in how they are expected to act as husbands, fathers, siblings. The two roles the Jameses assume influence one another, with Billington finding that 'Munro skilfully interweaves the personal and the political' (2014, non-paginated). In reference to James IV's time as King, Hepburn (2023) explains that

[t]he 'court' and the 'household' were distinct, yet closely related. The court was the space around the king and the people who occupied it, while the household was the formal structure at the heart of this space and population. It provided a framework which shaped the whole court.

(p. 14)

The concept of a royal household then is different from the contemporary understanding of a domestic sphere. Nonetheless, it is pertinent to the reading of *The James Plays* to consider how the political and personal identities of the Jameses inform one another. The wider political issues of the trilogy are prominent. Each king struggles with factitious infighting as well as a prolonged threat of invasion and war with the neighbouring English Kingdom (Munro, 2016). But how these seismic political events affect and define the character of the Jameses is at the forefront of the analysis. The distinct – but overlapping – challenges the Jameses encounter in their leadership positions and personal lives is analysed in greater detail in Chapters 4 and 5 respectively, with Chapter 6 discussing their subversion of hegemonic masculine traits. Before this, I give a literature review that clarifies the reading that underpins the subsequent method and methodology chapter.

Chapter 3. Literature Review

Demonstrating the complexity of Munro's engagement with masculinity, male identity and nationhood necessitates the use of several frameworks, for a layered, detailed analysis. To apply these lenses to a textual analysis of the trilogy, a robust comprehension of each individual framework must be acquired, to sufficiently build upon the context outlined in the previous chapter. This thematic literature review presents the work engaged with to achieve this. With the focus of this study being the relationship between masculinity, male identity, leadership and nationhood, masculinity studies serves as the primary framework *The James Plays* is studied through. In defining masculinities, the nature and presentation of male identity in Munro's writing is articulated. Thereafter, hegemonic masculinity theory establishes the dominance of a particular form of masculinity; one that authority is defined by. Through feminist theory, the nature of patriarchy is clarified, detailing the formation of gender hierarchies. Finally, the manner in which gender is conveyed and understood is explained through gender studies. This clarifies how Munro's trilogy contributes to the representation of Scottish masculinity and male identity in response to the political discourse present at the time.

Two perspectives on the formation of masculinity are outlined by Phillips (2006). First, there is the suggestion that 'boys and men are born with some amount of innate maleness or masculinity that is fixed and will evolve or develop in a biologically predetermined manner, identified as male, within a relatively narrow range of normality' (p. 404). In short, this argument indicates that one's conduct is an a priori attribute, which will develop regardless of external influences. An alternative argument is 'that babies are born into a culture that begins creating or defining them as male or female from "in utero" (if biological sex is known or assumed) or from birth' (p. 404), where culture invokes gender roles in what is referred to as social determinism (Anderson, 2023). This is the complete inverse of the prior argument, depicting masculinity as a posterior, something that is constructed from the cultural landscape that they are born into. This study is inclined towards the latter perspective, viewing masculinity – or rather, the presentation of masculinity – as a social construct. The Jameses amend their behaviour in accordance to hegemonic masculine ideals. Their masculine identity is shown to exist in relation to notions of masculinity within their culture. In her writing, Munro's

representation of gender is of an individual identity in relation to a social and cultural context.

Seagar and Barry argue that '[s]cientific evidence indicates that social factors shape the *expression* of gender identity rather than creating gender itself' (2019, p. 113: authors' own emphasis), where presentations of masculinity (as well as femininity) are processed and interpreted by the individual; a view that works in tandem with gender performativity, which will be described later in this chapter. This is applicable to the masculinities of the Jameses. As will be detailed in the textual analysis of the three plays, the three Kings show how attitudes and judgements are applied to male identity from childhood through to their adulthood, with their capability as a man in their private and public lives being defined by these views. Within a patriarchal society, structures define specific ideals and restraints on 'appropriate' expression of masculinity.

Huggins (2012) explains that 'masculinity has always been *constructed* and *manufactured* within specific institutional settings. Masculinity is not a mere biological identity since cultural and social power structures, while usually diverse, play a key role in shaping it' (p. 150: author's own emphasis). Masculinity inhabits an artificiality, one that is dictated by the society. As 'hegemonic masculinities plural are constructed at the local, regional and global level, where they manifest and develop in various ways' (Connell and Messerschmidt, 2005 cited in Ricciardelli, Maier and Hannah-Moffat, 2015, p. 494: authors own emphasis), the Jameses are evaluated through their social context, indicative of how male identity is formed in relation to cultural values in real life.

The plurality of the definition acknowledges that masculinity can be 'understood as a discursive practice – that is, as a communicative negotiatory and active gambit and thus also as open, fluid and heterogeneous' (Sørensen, 2000, p. 46), resulting in a masculinity being dependent on the hegemony level it operates in relation to.

Huggins (2012) believes that hegemonic masculinities will 'vary and change over time and in space' (p. 150), thus resulting in both its expression and influence being especial to nations and the communities that comprise it. Considering how these are depicted in *The James Plays* will convey how Munro's trilogy reflects the Scotland it

was written in, where masculinity has a unique expression that both informs and is informed by national identity and cultural attitudes.

In a patriarchal society, an individualistic form of masculinity will define that culture's 'ideal' form of masculinity. Messerschmidt (2012) explains that 'the concept of hegemonic masculinity was originally formulated to conceptualize how patriarchal relations are legitimated throughout society' (p. 63). This view is reiterated by Seymour (2003), who argues that "hegemonic masculinity' is a means of legitimizing patriarchy, making the dominance of men and the subordination of women within the 'gender order' appear natural and just, rather than a historically contingent and political system of oppression' (p. 224). It is a component of an oppressive societal structure that is cyclical in nature; those who conform to it reinforce patriarchy, thus compelling conformity. In more detail,

[w]hat hegemonic masculinity does so effectively is exemplify, at a macrostructural level, a masculinist ethos that privileges what have traditionally been seen as natural male traits. One could proceed to describe this in terms of a dominant ideology of masculinism: an ideology which seeks to sanction the cultural boundaries of 'masculine behaviour' while 'naturalizing' the sex/gender categories of man/woman.

(Whitehead, 1999, p. 58)

Where patriarchy implements a male dominance in society, one's standing within these arbitrary constraints is determined by an adherence to what is defined as dominant masculine conduct. This is seen in *The James Plays*, where each king finds a necessity to adopt particular masculine behaviours and attitudes in service of maintaining control of their court and, by proxy, their nation. Additionally, the king is a representative of the nation. The characteristics they inhabit and exhibit will be reflective of the country's normative concepts of masculine identity and behaviour. Through the Jameses, Munro critiques contemporary Scotland, where leadership – from family life, to business, to governance – is valued by masculine traits.

There are 'alternatives to hegemonic masculinity that promote more inclusive, empathetic, caring, and egalitarian forms of manhood' (Lomas, 2013, quoted in Pérez-Martínez *et al*, 2023, p. 469). Due to subverting the hegemonic ideal, they are poorly placed to be successful in patriarchal structures. Hearn and Parkin explain:

Within many models of leadership, the necessary and desirable qualities are assumed to be masculine. This assumption is deeply

entrenched in thinking and language, so that the language of leadership often equates with the language of masculinity to include qualities such as aggression, assertiveness, abrasiveness, and competitiveness.

(1986, p. 38)

In 21st century culture, being a leader is synonymous with oppressive traits.

Consequently, those who do not present these characteristics must either adopt them if they wish to pursue leadership positions, or see themselves be ostracised. In *The James Plays*, three national leaders are seen to contort their masculinity in accordance to the expectations of the hegemonic structures. Through the Jameses, Munro accentuates how male identity is curtailed in pursuit of power, respect and authority.

As stated in the previous chapter, the trilogy presents a male-dominant political sphere ingrained with attitudes to how masculinity should be presented. Ferguson notes that feminist theory is an apt framework for studying male identity, saying: 'Feminist theory is not only about women; it is about the world, engaged through critical intersectional perspectives. [...] It is rooted in and responsible to movements for equality, freedom, and justice' (2017, p. 269). The crux of this research paper's argument is that the Jameses display subversive masculinities that are moulded in response to hegemonic masculine ideals. These ideals are ingrained into systems built around patriarchy. Utilising feminist framework is effective in ascertaining how Munro's work reflects this. This thesis demonstrates how *The James Plays* represent social and cultural attitudes to masculinity and how this defines leadership and authority in a national context. Additionally, citing the intersectional nature of the framework vindicates the use of several complimentary frameworks to convey the complexity of Munro's representation.

Patriarchy presents 'a complex structure of gender relations in which the interrelation between different forms of masculinity and femininity plays a central role' (Demetriou, 2001, p. 343). Throughout *The James Plays*, the three James kings display varying subversive masculinities that do not adhere to the hegemonic masculine ideals of their social structures. Patriarchy sees an interplay between variations of identities, such as different forms of masculinity. This is conveyed by Grant and MacDonald (2020):

Complex gender hierarchies exist that are historically durable, on the one hand, while being open to contestation and change thanks to shifting ideas and material circumstances on the other. Thus, it is correct to say that systems of male privilege have dominated the West for hundreds of years *and* that struggles to rewrite the gender system are destabilizing the straightforward reproduction of those privileges.

(p. 373: authors' own emphasis)

As a western nation, Scotland is subject to the prioritisation of hegemonic masculinity in patriarchal structures. In studying the trilogy through the lens of feminist theory, the manner in which *The James Plays* conveys a gender system of male dominance – and how it is subverted – is outlined.

Where feminist theory examines societal inequality in the ethos of promoting change,

gender studies are not implicitly political in the sense of having an agenda for social change on the basis of gender equality. Instead, the principal aim has been one of raising awareness about the ways in which gender affects individual life choices and chances, and thus women's and men's relative personal opportunities for personal and career success.

(Mendes and Carter, 2008, p. 1702)

In this study, feminist theory highlights the way in which patriarchy implements a male-dominant society, with hegemonic masculinity and masculinity studies showing how forms of masculinity are generated and placed within this structure. Gender studies aligns with masculinity studies, considering how one's gender will influence identity and their social standing. Through an engagement with gender performativity, the way in which one embodies and presents their gender is understood. In short, it presents a 'theory of gender, or the body, as one that acts and performs according to the conventions of gender, conventions that are influenced, from the start, before one is even born' (Butler and Barbec, 2017, no pagination). The Jameses depict how masculine identity is defined and assessed against long-standing conventions on gender identity. With each James being a part of an authoritative power structure, they condense a representation of contemporary Scottish culture, where alternative masculinities are curtailed by hegemonic ideals.

Masculinity is expressed in accordance to social cues that communicate a unilateral perception of masculinity, with one's 'success' being decreed by an adherence to these traits.

The act that one does, the act that one performs, is, in a sense, an act that has been going on before one arrived on the scene. Hence, gender is an act which has been rehearsed, much as a script survives the particular actors who make use of it, but which requires individual actors in order to be actualized and reproduced as reality once again. The complex components that go into an act must be distinguished in order to understand the kind of acting in concert and acting in accord which acting one's gender invariably is.

(Butler, 1988, p. 526)

The way gender is conceived and perceived relies upon concepts ingrained within one's culture. Male identity, like any other gender identity, is depicted through a series of characteristics and traits that operate to convey the gender that the individual associates their identity with. The way the Jameses present themselves in their leadership position is informed by their culture and, in turn, informs their culture. They exhibit how masculine identity is reflective of the notions of masculinity that exist in societies.

To articulate gender, behaviours and modes of expression are adopted to convey this component of identity. Butler further explains that

acts, gestures, and desire produce the effect of an internal core or substance, but produce this *on the surface* of the body, through play of signifying absences that suggest, but never reveal, the organizing principle of identity as a cause. Such acts, gestures, enactments, generally construed, are *performative* in the sense that the essence or identity that they otherwise purport to express are fabrications manufactured and sustained through corporeal signs and other discursive means.

(1999, p. 173: authors own emphasis)

A masculinity is conveyed through certain actions that are indicative of masculinity in the individual's culture. In *The James Plays*, the three Jameses demonstrate how masculine identity is expected to adhere to particular perceptions of male identity. As will be explored in the coming chapters, there are various instances where the James monarchs are defined against hegemonic masculinity and thereafter amend themselves to be seen more favourably by their contemporaries. Prayitno *et al* (2024) describe how men feel compelled to adhere to societal expectations for the male gender, or risk being alienated. If one is masculine-presenting, a compulsion exists to express this through established social norms. But, as the term 'performativity' implies, it is an adherence to associations, not necessarily an authentic form of expression.

When studying how the three James monarchs have their masculinity valued and influenced by their social setting, masculinity studies enhances the understanding of male identity in response to external factors. This framework offers perspectives on the formation of masculinity and how patriarchal structures will influence the development and presentation of male identity. The role of patriarchal attitudes is given further detail through hegemonic masculinity theory. The dominance of this masculine identity is explored, with insight on how alternative masculinities are valued in relation to this ideal; a matter of particular relevance in the analysis of the James monarchs. As an intersectional framework, feminist theory is used in this research project to highlight the nature of a patriarchal society, a recurrent factor the selected lenses. Through gender studies, the way an individual communicates their gender through social and cultural cues is articulated, framing how and why the Jameses express themselves in relation to their context. In the following chapter, the way these are applied through a textual analysis is explained.

Chapter 4. Method and Methodology

Theatre holds an 'innate complexity and uniqueness in how it can affect individuals' (Brown and Novak-Leonard, 2013, p. 223), indicating the extent of subjectivity to how plays can be received. To offer an analysis on a particular reading of the plays, the method and methodology must be well considered. In order to contextualise the plays within their political landscape, I engage the opinions of critics. Barrett (2010) suggests considering critics as scholars when studying theatre, in the interest of viewing it as a subject of research, rather than evaluating 'the work as product' (p. 135). In doing so, *The James Plays* are read within the context of the political climate of the 2014 independence referendum, which is used as a platform to analyse contemporary Scottish culture. Through a study of the James kings, it will be argued that Munro criticises the social structures that dictate masculinities and male identity, as well as associated negotiations of power and definitions of nationhood.

Through a textual analysis, how a text reflects the culture it is written in is ascertained. Carley explains:

Through analyzing texts the interplay between human cognition and culture can be examined. Through analyzing texts cognitive similarities and differences across individuals, which serve as a basis for culture can be described. Through analyzing texts the impact of culture on individual behaviour can be examined. In addition, such analyses can locate the similarities and differences across cultures and changes within cultures.

(1994, p. 291)

By critically evaluating the text, it can be determined how Munro engages with Scottish masculine identity and the relationship between masculinity and leadership. In doing a textual analysis, there is no intent to make a statement on what Rona Munro's views precisely are. Rather, a textual analysis permits an 'educated guess at some of the most likely interpretations that might be made of that text' (McKee, 2003, p. 1). Having contextualised both Munro and her trilogy in the landscape of Scottish theatre and the political climate of 2014, this project offers arguments on how the writing of *The James Plays* responds to these matters through the character drama.

'Patriarchy's defining elements are its male-dominated, male-identified, and male-centred character' explains Johnson (2013, p. 29), that is 'about the valuing of maleness and masculinity' (p. 29). To outline Munro's critique of this, I undertake a textual analysis, with the aid of frameworks. In this instance, the textual analysis is conducted through the intersectional lenses of masculinity studies, hegemonic masculinity theory, feminist theory and gender studies. Brown (2016) finds that '[t]he theme of feminine agency and power is key to Munro's (her)story plays, offering a counterhistory to one dominated by men and patriarchy' (pp. 210-211). This research follows an alternative line of thought, considering how masculinities are shown to compete within hegemonic structures. Whilst it is accurate to say male-superiority is promoted in patriarchy, there is some nuance in how this has been critiqued by Munro. In *The James Plays*, there is an exploration of how male identity is informed by its social and cultural context in pursuit of authority, rather than simply saying that masculine identity is innately privileged. In accordance to this, several frameworks are used in the study of the trilogy. By considering Munro's writing through multiple lenses, a layered methodology is created that serves to articulate the complexity of identity that her characters represent.

In outlining the methods and methodology of this project, the efficacy of a textual analysis in studying the *James* trilogy is stated, highlighting the benefits to dissecting the text to derive meaning. The multiple frameworks informing the textual analysis complement one another in detailing how social structures define and influence gender identity and its associated hierarchies. The following three chapters present the findings of this textual analysis of *The James Plays*. Firstly, the way hegemonic masculinity defines leadership and power is explored through James I and James III. Thereafter, it is shown how James II and James III's personal and private lifestyles are influenced by hegemonic masculinity. The final chapter of the textual analysis presents the ways hegemonic masculine ideals are challenged through the depiction of James I and James II.

Chapter 5. Hegemonic masculinity, leadership and power in *The James Plays*

As representatives of their nation, the Jameses are influenced by hegemonic masculine ideals in pursuit of power and control. In this chapter, James I abandoning his skill in diplomacy in favour of aggressive, nationalist rhetoric is examined. Following this, James III's abusive nature is evaluated in relation to his status as king, to consider how a position of power can lead to such domineering behaviour. By conducting this analysis, how Munro critiques the nature of power and authority in contemporary Scotland is explained.

James I: The Key Will Keep the Lock opens with Scottish prisoners of war encountering King Henry V of England with the imprisoned Scottish king, James I. As Henry holds James I's cousins hostage, he is pressed to determine the sentence for their treachery – his cousins have, after all, fought an army that the Scottish king stood with. Where James I adheres to a what he states are '[t]he laws of engagement and the rules of chivalry' (Munro, 2016, p. 9), Henry encourages him to utilise alternative, more violent measures. Goading him, Henry says: 'Tell them what they're missing, James, tell them what a brilliant king you'd be. Dazzle them. Let them see your regal power, your strength, they need to see your *strength*, James' (p. 9: author's own emphasis). From the very beginning of the play cycle, the king, as a male authority figure, is expected to show force and assert himself through aggression.

Here, James I's status as king is used as justification for domineering conduct. It is not so much a framing of Scottish values against English values; this is incidental to the interpersonal conflict of the two leaders. Rather, it is the first interrogation of conflicting attitudes to male leadership. Against a ruthless appeal for violence and domination is a measured, diplomatic response. Considering this in relation to the referendum period it was written in, it is a discussion of what form of leadership the nation aspires for. With a referendum posing questions on how Scotland ought to be led, James I and Henry represent two opposing attitudes. The subversiveness of contemporary rationality and respect are positioned against historic aggression and forcefulness. Through James and Henry's debate, a leader who seeks to be open-minded and rule-abiding is evaluated alongside the hegemonic masculine archetype

of an isolationist, reactive leader. James I exemplifies the form leadership should take in a progressive nation.

James I's subversion of hegemonic masculine traits is mocked by Henry:

What kind of king can't order an execution?

What kind of king is brought up in a prison reading books and writing poetry? What good will that do Scotland when I come to burn you down? What would you do, James? Stand at the border and shout a few verses at me to send me home? It might just work too, this stuff's diabolical.

(Munro, 2016, p. 10)

Where his reluctance to resort to violence is ridiculed, the specific targeting of his interests is significant. Traditionally, masculine hobbies are viewed as being those that are more practical and physically challenging, with an interest in the likes of literature being seen as a feminine interest (Springer and Mouzon, 2019). Henry's insults act both as an attack on his character and his capability as a leader.

Within the narrative, hegemonic masculine traits are synonymous with leadership traits. James I's subversion of masculine ideals has him viewed as a weak male; thus, a weak king. Henry reiterates these attitudes by threatening to hang the prisoners 'while your King reads you verses' (Munro, 2016, p. 11). Conveyed here is the societal expectation that leaders should not only present hegemonic masculine ideals, but embody them. The qualities associated with the position must be integral to the individual assuming it. After all, the perceptions of authority are not a cause of patriarchy, but a consequence of it: patriarchy will 'regularly punish those who do their gender wrong' (Butler, 2009, p. 178). Because of his perceived short-comings, James I is disrespected and devalued. His subversive masculinity being ridiculed reflects how these strict structures will undermine the capacity for differing forms of masculine identity to be viewed as equal, let alone as an authoritative leader. In the sparring of a Scottish and English leader, a subversive masculinity clashes with a male identity that conforms to hegemonic masculine ideals. As contemporary Scotland debated the governance of the nation, Munro engages with the nature of leadership, positioning two forms of male authority against one another.

Seeking to strain the relationship between James I and his subjects, Henry points out that during all the years of his imprisonment, the Scottish court never sought to pay the ransom for his release. In retaliation to this, James's cousin Walter declares: 'He's your *prisoner* King, he's no *my* King' (Munro, p. 7: author's own emphasis). It is clarified by James I to Joan in a later scene that he was captured by English pirates as a young boy when escaping to France for refuge, after the death of his older brother. Despite his vulnerability as a child, Walter seemingly holds him accountable for his own captivity. James I's ability to be king is framed through this. A disdain for the English discredits James in some peoples' eyes, with Walter being a fervent example of this. His declaration that James is 'King Henry's prisoner. Not my King. Not my fucking King!' (p. 57) reflects a sense of national identity that is influenced by the nature of their leader. Instead of leading Scotland against England in battle, he is imprisoned there. Rather than scorning the English (as the Scottish prisoners do when initially captured), he instead collaborates with King Henry in pursuit of peace between the Kingdoms.

Walter depicts those who define Scottish identity purely in relation to England, viewing current political stress as part of a centuries-long tirade against Scottish culture. James I's incarceration – specifically to the English – emasculates him, once again being used as reason to see him as a weak leader. National leadership and male identity are intertwined, where non-hegemonic masculine values are deemed insufficient in upholding Scottish values. Where James I presents a desire to build a partnership with England on mutual terms, Walter shows how the English are positioned by some to enhance male identity within nationalist movements. In this tension, the nature of Scottish national leadership is scrutinised, positioning a reactionary, Anglophobic nationalism against the diplomacy of an outward-looking Scotland. Differing attitudes inherent in Scottish nationalism are portrayed in a hostile, competitive nature. The valuing of national leadership is subjected to the valuing of masculinities. James I and Henry represent the posturing of male authority in an international context. Walter and his attitudes of James represent the competing visions of male authority in a national context. In the referendum, only two options were presented to the electorate. Munro demonstrates that there are a plethora of competing beliefs and values in what sort of nation Scotland should be.

Even amongst those who would be considered to be on the same side politically, there is disagreement in what form governance should take.

After James I's coronation, reservations amongst the Scottish elite over the extent of his Scottish identity persist. At the end of the ceremony, James I argues that he cannot truly be king until everyone kneels to him and the queen; this is met by '[a] nasty silence' (Munro, 2016, p. 41). This is determined by members of the court to be an English custom, not a Scottish one, which leads James to state: 'You think I'm an Englishman' (p. 42). When his cousin, Big James, answers in the affirmative, James I then asks: 'Do I sound like an Englishman?' (p. 42). Where the nature of English relations has had a bearing on how Scottish national identity is perceived, here the contrasting views come to a head. He expresses concern that they 'don't know who I am and it looks likely I'm an Englishman... or an English servant anyway' (p. 42). With James I's subjugation to the English monarch being (in his eyes) internalised, he begins to gauge that his reputation is greatly marred by this. His Scottish identity is perceived in relation to the English crown. Certainly, the way his masculine identity is perceived is rooted in this. In the lead up to this exchange with Big James, the monarch is mistreated during the ceremony. He is attended to roughly, with Scottish nobles '*getting a bit of the robing wrong, deliberately*' (Munro, 2016, p. 38). Whilst these are covert slights against the monarch, the deliberate maliciousness of the acts speak of how they view James I. Due to his imprisonment at the hands of their enemy, he is viewed as lesser. By giving credence to Henry's suggestion that he is 'the king nobody wants (p. 9), they demonstrate that he is viewed as subordinate to them because of how he presents himself as a man.

The court only comes to show respect when James I declares: 'I want you to kneel to Scotland. That's who I am now, in my body, in my person, I'm the King of Scots. That's what I was born to' (Munro, 2016, p. 43), making himself synonymous with the Scottish people and the nation herself. He antagonises the neighbouring Kingdom, saying: 'England has pursued our wealth and bled our wealth for a hundred years or more and looks ready to do it for hundreds more until this is a nation of beggars. Then they'll flick us a coin of our own stolen gold and call it charity' (p. 44), depicting them as a force that must be overcome. James I's staunch defence of Scottish revenue highlights aspects of the debate that focused on the nation's financial

autonomy, evoking nationalist sentiment that Scotland is exploited by England. A core argument in the Scottish National Party (SNP)'s campaign material, *Scotland's Future*, is 'that Scotland has the financial foundations to be a successful independent country' (Scottish Government, 2013), positioning Scotland's self-determination on the nation's wealth. In this short exchange between James I and his court, Munro concisely portrays attitudes inherent in the campaign for Scottish independence. In a wider context, he reflects contemporary arguments that 'advocate separatism on the grounds that England predominates within the Union, that the English impose policies based on English values and that, therefore, a 'Scottish' way of life is impossible within Britain' (Sindic and Reicher, 2009, p. 117). He represents a conception that the truest form of Scottish identity can exist only with independence.

The assertive stance James takes is indicative of the hegemonized masculinity within Scottish nationalism Gibbs and Scothorne (2020) spoke of. The court rallies around the message that their underdog nation will rise against the oppression of the English establishment. James says that kneeling to him will 'show me how much you love this country' (p. 45), further emboldening the unity of leader and state, and establishing that following him is a patriotic act. In a rather frank assessment, Hutchison (1999) suggests nationalists are incentivised by a 'need to belong and by a revulsion against established institutions' (pp. 393-394). Where James has otherwise demonstrated skill in negotiation, diplomacy and courtesy, here this is discarded in favour of enticing a reactionary court to his side. This suggests that, regardless of the nature of the individual assuming the leadership position, they will be malleable to the attitudes ingrained within a patriarchal structure. James I, who had demonstrated diplomacy and was belittled by another leader and his court, only finds obedience by adhering to hegemonic masculine behaviours. Whilst James did this against both a neighbouring Kingdom and his court, he is also asserting his authority over other men: King Henry, as the leader of England; and James I's family (who are also Scottish nobles), who sought to demean him during the ceremony.

In the trilogy, James III is the monarch who depicts hegemonic masculine traits the most. In the fourth scene of Act 1, James III accuses his brother Sandy of plotting against him, saying: 'You speak against me in parliament. You've got a very cosy little gang there with all your neighbours. What else are you all talking about when

you're not shouting me down?' (Munro, 2016, p. 212). When his views are challenged, he adopts an accusatorial stance; utilising and reinforcing his status to silence opposition. Rather than rely on the counsel of those around him, he instead sees conspiracies to usurp him. With power within patriarchal structures being contingent on a hierarchy of masculinities, James III looks to enhance his leadership through domineering behaviour against other men; here, by making an example of his brother. Leadership in hegemonic structures demands assertion and domination to maintain authority. James III is the trilogy's representation of how this will ingrain itself further into culture and society over time.

At a surface level, *James III* is the concluding piece of the cycle by the simple fact that it is the final instalment. However, with the direct lineage of James III's predecessors and their turn to ruthlessness to enforce authority, this play exemplifies the manner in which hegemonic masculinity is embodied in accordance to cultural expectations for male identity. As a consequence, the presentation of masculinity evolves into more domineering and ruthless forms. When his son, Jamie, says: 'You can't kill him!' (Munro, 2016, p. 213), James III replies: 'Actually, you know I can. Being the King' (p. 213). For him, his status is reason enough to behave how he likes; in turn, his behaviour will maintain his status. Isaksson (2020) finds that patriarchy facilitates 'an increasingly corrupt male morality that had considerable consequences for the idea of the ethical and democratic society' (p. 6). James III is representative of how the valuing of hegemonic masculine traits results in an intensification of masculine presentation. The competitiveness of gendered hierarchies produce more extreme forms of masculine identity in pursuit of authority.

James I used the antagonization of England to establish his commitment to the Scottish people. James III differs from this, showing a flippant attitude to threat of invasion. His wife, Margaret, chastises him for his poor etiquette in parliament, saying: 'These are the men you *need* if you ever want to raise an army! They're your only defence against invasion!' (Munro, 2016, p. 228: authors own emphasis). This prompts a rant from James III:

Let England invade! I'll be *delighted* to surrender. Save a lot of time and money and all that wasted effort bouncing around waving our fists and kidding on we're not just a wee boy without a catapult facing up to a bear.

Let England *eat* us and get it over with! What's the point! What's the point? Today, tomorrow, a hundred years from now? They'll do it one day, won't they? They're bigger than us! They've got more money! Face the reality, dearest! They're having us! Let's get it over with and get on with something that makes sense of our imminent plummet into an open grave!

(p. 228: authors own emphasis)

Expressed here is an exasperation of continually mitigating the threat. To an extent, this could be seen as a departure from hegemonic masculine traits, with James III decrying the nation he leads as one that is weak and primed to be conquered in the imminent future. However, it is short sighted to make this analysis contingent on one particular demonstration of hegemonic masculinity. '[A]lthough it used to be believed that culture was "shared" among its constituents,' explains Schak (2005, p. 302), 'it is now well recognised that, particularly in complex societies, there is a variety of sub-cultures or perhaps variations on cultural themes.' Munro is not exploring Scottish masculinity as a general concept. She is engaging with contemporary Scottish masculine identities. James I and James III both adhere to hegemonic masculine characteristics to establish and maintain authority. In their contrasting attitudes to England, Munro demonstrates that hegemonic masculinity will present itself in different contexts, rooted in different values. Again, it is the nature of leadership and authority in contemporary Scotland she is critical of, not the particular beliefs underlying it.

James III's lack of commitment to leadership is an attribute of his elevated sense of self, where he places his importance over that of the people he leads. As king, he accuses members of the elite of 'sitting on my taxes' (Munro, 2016, p. 220). He is keen to tell Margaret that she has 'forgotten who [she's] speaking to' (Munro, 2016, p. 220) when she tells him he cannot afford his spending plans, demonstrating a belief he should not be spoken against. This is a consequence of the power structure he operates in. Kalish & Kimmel argue: 'Aggrieved entitlement is a product of hegemonic masculinity' (2010, quoted in Scheuerman, 2021, p. 210). James is representative of this entitlement, seeking ownership of the nation's revenue – much of which is so he can be escorted by his own choir (Munro, 2016) – and taking exception to being spoken down to. Later in the play, he tells the court:

This is who I am.

This is how God made me.

I was your opportunity for greatness and you *blew* it.

God made me a king... but I can't be the king of mice. Your tiny rodent brains couldn't even comprehend what I offered you.

(p. 284: author's own emphasis)

Here, James is explicitly hubristic and arrogant. The integration of hegemonic masculinity into leadership across the trilogy culminates here, with James seeing his leadership as his right, with those who express disapproval being belittled. He portrays the intensification of hegemonic structures in patriarchal societies, where the perceived value is within the leader, not the system that facilitates the leadership.

Margerat offers an alternative perspective on James III's conduct. Earlier in the play, as Phemy bemoans James' lacking abilities as a leader, such as crop failures, Margaret responds: 'He's a king but he's just a man. Everyone wants him to make the world perfect just because he looks as if he ought to be able to do it' (pp. 225-226). From this perspective, James III is simply adopting the characteristics that are expected of him; people expect something by way of divine intervention, and so he embodies a divine complex. Here, the toxic traits exhibited are framed as a product of the system he is a part of. In every instalment of *The James Plays*, the Jameses are shown to suppress their subversive masculine traits and replace them with hegemonic masculine ones, to maintain their leadership. Through this dialogue, Munro articulates her critique of the social and cultural values that are imposed upon masculine identities. Englar-Carlson suggests that 'the failure to meet the cultural expectations of masculinity also appears to be detrimental, as others may evaluate men harshly for not living up to societal expectations of what it means to be a man' (2006, p. 24). This echoes Butler's (2009) earlier sentiment that people will face punishment for not successfully adhering to the expectations bestowed upon their gender.

In his official capacity, James I is seen to discard his efforts to appease and negotiate in favour of embodying a heroic masculine archetype, rallying his court to his side with a defiant, assertive speech against England (Munro, 2016). This is relevant in a Scotland in the midst of a debate on independence. The Scottish nationalist movement has a history of some sectors promoting a hegemonized

masculinity that sought to fight against English oppression (Gibbs and Scothorne, 2020). By tapping into attitudes within Scottish nationalism, Munro creates a wider discussion on how leadership is valued when it depicts traits associated with hegemonic masculinity.

Isaksson (2020) argues that patriarchal power structures lead to the eventual corruption of male morality, which is seen at the end of the trilogy with James III. He displays a paranoia when challenged. Eventually, he reveals the extent of his hubris, claiming ownership of the nation's finances for his own indulgence and antagonising anyone who seeks to prevent his efforts (Munro, 2016). The level of entitlement that comes within hegemonic masculinity (Scheuerman, 2021) is seen in James III, who uses his status to emphasise his seniority and authority in every situation.

Chapter 6. Personal and private lifestyles and hegemonic masculinity in *The James Plays*

By studying the personal relationships of James II and James III, an overview of how hegemonic masculinity ingrains itself into males from childhood to adulthood is offered. In the former, the traumatic experiences of his childhood haunt him, where an unwanted father figure conducts himself in an aggressive, domineering fashion. In the latter, his fear of losing power to his son further instils his abrasive behaviour. An analysis of James III's sexual identity suggests that the hegemonic masculine characteristics he is compelled to exhibit stand in opposition to his internal identity. Munro explores how progressions in Scottish masculinity are curtailed and restrained by social and cultural attitudes in hegemonic structures.

For a sizable portion of the second instalment, James II is shown to be gripped in the fear of his childhood trauma. As Act 1 begins, it is stated that '*everything we see is either nightmare or heightened memory*' (Munro, 2016, p. 93), the narrative moving through defining moments of James II's early years. As he recalls meeting John Stewart, his mother's new partner, '*[t]he nightmare is also closing in on JAMES, a memory of his father's death*' (p. 99). Through the absence of a father figure, James II is exposed to demonstrations of aggression and emasculation by male figures. In showing this, Munro gives an unfettered presentation of how hegemonic masculinity informs male behaviour from a young age.

Early in the play, James II's mother tells him that John Stewart is now his father, with James being quite candid in saying:

'My father's dead.

'My father was a hero' (Munro, 2016, p. 99).

This explicitly shows that James still holds his father dearly and is reluctant to replace him with a new parental figure. John Stewart counters this affection, seeking to belittle James II's father. When left alone with James, Stewart says: 'If your father was here I'd cut his legs and leave him sitting in his own blood watching me give your mother what he never could. And I'll do the same to you if you don't shut up' (Munro, 2016, p. 99). As a child, James II is exposed to this aggressive masculinity, with Stewart seeking to portray a superior masculine identity by depicting James's father as a weak male. Further to this, it reinforces the sex/gender divide hegemonic

masculinity enforces, treating women as subservient to men, where 'sex should be used to dominate women' (Murnen, Wright, and Kaluzny, 2002, p. 370). John Stewart uses it to position himself as superior to James I. His ideation of violence and sexual conquest is extended against James II himself, seeking subservience by threatening him in a frank fashion, whilst speaking of his mother with this puerile attitude. The extent to which hegemonic masculine values are instilled into young boys is conveyed in this interaction, where these values and traits are presented as typical male behaviour. 'One of the most important circumstances of young people's lives is the gender order that they live in,' argues Connell (2005). 'Masculinities are constructed, over time, in young people's encounters with a system of gender relations' (p. 13). Through James II and John Stewart's relationship, Munro presents how a masculine identity is developed in accordance to or against the masculinities they interact with at a young age. Through the medieval politics of the play, she holds a mirror up to contemporary Scotland, challenging how masculinity and the exploitation of women are instilled into male psyches from childhood.

When he is found in a frantic state at the end of Act 1, James II tells his new wife, Mary: 'I just have nightmares sometimes. You don't need to be scared' (Munro, 2016, p. 131). Laterally, he tells William: 'Jesus, Will... she saw me climb in the kist, like a frightened bairn' (p. 132). Shown here is a belief that he should appear braver and stronger in front of his wife, despite the impact his nightmares and memories have on him. His dismissive and belittling attitude conveys how 'men distressed by self-perceived deficiencies in their masculinity must contend with vulnerable emotions (e.g., fear, shame) which themselves deviate from gender-emotion norms dictating dominance and restricted emotional expression' (Berke, Reidy and Zeichner, 2018, non-paginated). James II represents the debilitating stricture imposed on male-expression, where suppressing reactions to difficult events results in further emotional challenges. The way men process and address experiences is dictated by the hegemonic structures they exist within, exemplified in James II's shame of showing perceived weakness in front of others.

James III is unreserved in displaying and acting upon his anger. This is seen in the third scene of Act 1. After his brother, Sandy, leaves their intense exchange, James III decries him a traitor. Jamie goes against his father, declaring that Sandy is not.

In the heat of his anger, 'JAMES goes to hit him. MARGARET restrains JAMES, furious' (p. 213). In response to her intervention, he 'turns on her, terrifyingly angry' being described as 'lost in himself, trying to hold it together, breathless with rage' (p. 213). In the interest of power, violence presents itself as an immediate form of enforcement. 'In particular, the culture of violence associated with aggrieved entitlement is the way it is [...] because violence is viewed as a valid way for men to assert their masculinity' (Kalish & Kimmel, 2010, cited in Scheuerman, 2021, p. 210). A culture that defines leadership by hegemonic masculinity will inform concepts of seniority across all areas of a society. James III reflects this in his dual role as national leader and family member. As leader, he represents the nature of leadership of Scotland. In his family dynamic, he demonstrates how this informs interactions in familial relationships. Just as traits like aggression and competitiveness are used to establish authority in the political arena, so too are they used in personal relationships.

Aggression of all forms – not just physical – is relied upon to maintain status by male figures, as patriarchal structures will see 'men engage in hypermasculine pursuits in response to inferior feelings' (Anderson, 2023, p. 1). With James III, a sense of insecurity and inferiority is compensated with extreme demonstrations of hegemonic masculine behaviours. What makes James's behaviour as noteworthy here is not only that it is his son he is going against but that such a level of aggression comes to the fore against a child. His suspicion of being undermined by his council – despite his perceived divine right as king – bleeds into his attitude as a father. He is consumed by an unabashed presumption that he ought to be obeyed and agreed with, regardless of the circumstances. If hegemonic masculinity is seen as an appropriate and respected form of masculinity in a societal context, it will in turn be seen as such on a smaller, personal scale.

When Jamie asks why his father hates him, James III's Aunt Annabelle tells him: 'Because you're the end of him. If you live' (Munro, 2016, p. 217). It is not the threat but the inevitability of this that goads James III, his actions portraying an effort to control something beyond his control. Jamie insists he would never hurt his father, with Annabella replying: 'No. But you're what's coming next' (p. 217). Seemingly, Jamie is a reminder to James of his own mortality and the eventual loss of his

throne. As such, the desire for control supersedes his paternal responsibilities, distancing him from his son in favour of his leadership status. Through this strained relationship, Munro critiques the prioritisation of male success in hegemonic structures over the pursuit of healthy personal relationships.

James III's masculine identity, when considered in relation to his sexuality, suggests his behaviour is compensating for his subversive masculinity. James exhibits a toxic masculinity, described by Prayitno *et al* as

a concept created by society itself regarding how men should behave so as to create a "belief" that men must act in accordance with existing standards of masculinity. In order to receive social validation, they are required to meet the gender expectations set out in traditional norms regarding masculinity. Masculinity itself is characterized by legitimacy, leadership, and authority. If men are unable to display these attitudes, then they must be prepared to face social consequences.

(2024, p. 693)

As leader of the nation, James III is expected to fully embody a hegemonized masculinity, despite it being exclusionary of his identity. '[M]ost men gain some benefit from a hegemonic masculinity, but not all men gain equal benefit' Anderson (2023, p.1) explains, adding that straight men will find success much more easily than queer men. '[H]eterosexuality and homophobia have been considered fundamental components of hegemonic masculinity' (Grindstaff and West, 2011, p. 860), creating a dichotomy for James III. Where there is a necessity to adopt it, so too is there an incompatibility with hegemonic masculinity, generating a heightened masculine identity that leans toward toxic tendencies. This is in part due to the continued prioritisation of masculinity over femininity, where 'being gay has stereotypically and erroneously been equated with being "feminine", fear of femininity presents itself as homophobia' (Hong, 2000, p. 272). This insecurity results in 'demonstrations of control and agency, stoicism, emotional rigidity and inhibition, and an aversion to character traits associated with femininity' (Wilson et al, 2021, p. 2). James III portrays the necessity for subversive masculine identities to reject and discard attributes of their innate nature to be accepted within hegemonic structures.

Through James III, it is seen how a toxic masculine identity is given more credence in a patriarchal society than a queer masculine identity. 'The term *toxic masculinity* is useful in discussions about gender and forms of masculinity,' outlines Kupers

(2005), 'because it delineates those aspects of hegemonic masculinity that are socially destructive, such as misogyny, homophobia, greed, and violent domination' (p. 716, author's own emphasis). James III's reliance on violence has already been detailed in this chapter, as well as his greed for his authority as monarch. In addition to this, he is blatantly misogynistic, a notable example being his efforts to demean his wife by insulting her appearance. He gifts her a mirror just so he can say: 'Look how ugly you are' (Munro, 2016, p. 252). This behaviour is contingent on a 'culture that tolerates or even valorises toxic masculinities as an extension of hegemonic masculinities' (Conner *et al*, 2021, p. 9). *James III: The True Mirror*, as the concluding instalment, represents the cultural integration of hegemonic structures across the trilogy. Morrell, Jewkes and Lindegger (2012) argue that 'hegemonic masculinity [is] synonymous with problematic male attitudes and behavior, such as violence and abuse of women and children' (p. 13). James III's toxic masculinity demonstrates how an adherence to hegemonic masculine values will segue to bolder masculinities that intensify gender barriers and further reject subversive masculinities.

Connell (2005) argues that the presentation of masculinity is ingrained into men from a young age. In *James II: Day of the Innocents*, it is shown how prolific hegemonic masculine values are in the culture boys are brought up in. James II is exposed to the competitive nature of masculinity as a child through his encounter with John Stewart. Assuming the role as his paternal figure, John Stewart emasculates James II's father and exemplifies the subjugation of women – a prevalent attribute of hegemonic masculinity (Murnen, Wright, and Kaluzny, 2002) – by demeaning his mother as a sexual aspiration for his ego.

As Anderson (2023) explains, different masculinities will gain less from patriarchal structures that endorse hegemonic masculinities. As a queer man, James III exemplifies that there is a multiplicity of masculinities beyond the hegemonic ideal; but to maintain his position as a leader, he must suppress this side of his identity. He turns to aggression and violence to maintain control, behaviours used to embolden perceptions of masculinity (Scheuerman, 2021). James III represents the way in which hegemonic masculine ideals will be incorporated into one's character in pursuit of acceptance.

Chapter 7. The ways the play cycle challenge hegemonic masculine values

Despite leadership being so heavily defined in relation to hegemonic masculine values, there are departures from these characteristics amongst the James kings. In this chapter, the nature of James I's marriage to Joan will be evaluated alongside James II's friendship with William, demonstrating how these two monarchs nurtured values and dynamics beyond the ideals embowed upon them from their social settings. Through James I and II, Munro explores identities in contemporary Scotland that are defined outwith the values of hegemonic structures.

Although, as covered in a prior chapter, James I sought to bring his court to his side with nationalist rhetoric, he also seeks to garner respect for his wife, Joan. He states that members of the court 'have to kneel to me, and my Queen' (Munro, 2016, p. 41). He sees it as accepting him as king; thus, he is keen to establish Joan's authority in the court, too. With some members of the court querying the extent of James I's Scottish identity, it stands to reason that Joan being English will not sit well amongst some of the more reactionary of the group. As leader of Scotland, James I acts as a representative of the nation's values. James I leans towards ethnic nationalism to appeal to his nobles, before pushing towards a vision of civic nationalism. In having James I embrace the debate on national identity and what it means to be Scottish, two forms of Scottish nationalism are presented. Through James I, Munro offers a critical perspective on which form of nationalism better represents a contemporary, progressive Scotland.

In his efforts to persuade the court to his side, James I places value on his ethnic heritage. Holding his wrist up, he says:

'Blood. Royal Blood.

'[...] The same blood as my great great-grandfather, Robert the Bruce. The blood that made me a prisoner. The blood that made me a king' (Munro, 2016, p. 43).

On the surface, this is an appeal to his hereditary right to reign. However, when placed within the wider defence of his nationality, it highlights his heritage as a Scot, with further appeal through reference to the iconic figure of Robert the Bruce. This is married with anti-English statements aimed at the likes of Walter, who display a candid anti-English attitude. As discussed to some lengths in previous chapters, Scottish nationalism has had movements built against English institutes, arguing that

Scotland has been extensively exploited by their neighbouring nation. In this piece of dialogue, Munro has acutely drawn attention to forms of Scottish nationalism that exist on ethnic lines. It is depicted as exclusionary and reactionary, building a national identity in opposition to other nationalities.

James I expecting the same level of respect to be shown for his English partner is indicative of moving towards civic nationalism.

A 'civic' nation is generally understood as being based on two main aspects: belonging to a shared territory, rather than on the (apparent) blood-descent usually stressed by more ethnic nations; and allegiance to shared institutions, usually understood as the institutions of an independent state.

(Kearton, 2005, p. 27)

Although he has made a point of his heritage, he tells his court (in reference to Joan): 'The greatest jewel that England had is ours now. [...] What is Scotland's will stay with Scotland [...]' (Munro, 2016, p. 44). Whilst she is objectified to a degree in these remarks, Joan is given extensive value by James I and promoted as being a part of Scotland. He has moved beyond the value of heritage, instead placing her as a part of the Scottish nation. James believes '[t]hat Scotland will be small, but whole. It will be poor, but all its people will know their worth and how to fight for it' (Munro, 2016, p. 45). In saying this, he reflects notions of civic nationalism which values a unified nation that places value on every member of the population, regardless of their background. The SNP advocated for

an inclusive model of citizenship for people whether or not they define themselves as primarily or exclusively Scottish or wish to become a Scottish passport holder. People in Scotland are accustomed to multiple identities, be they national, regional, ethnic, linguistic or religious, and a commitment to a multi-cultural Scotland will be a cornerstone of the nation on independence.

(Scottish Government, 2013)

Munro's writing reflects beliefs in sections of the pro-independence campaign that Scottish nationality should be an inclusive, all-encompassing identity. In the argument for what citizenship in an independent Scotland should look like, Munro focuses on the nature of Scottish identity, presenting a perspective that is not exclusionary of any heritage.

Having detailed earlier that James I was devalued by his contemporaries for writing poetry, it is worth considering how his engagement with it represents an alternative,

subversive masculine identity. Hegemonic masculine attitudes, according to Greig and Hughes (2009) create a disinterest in poetry amongst men for two reasons. Firstly, there is a developed cultural attitude that it simply is not for men, reflecting an earlier argument by Springer and Mouzon (2019) on the gendered attitudes in these interests. Secondly, it is found that when engagement with poetry is encouraged amongst boys and men, 'it often celebrates, glorifies, and sanctions outdated, traditional definitions of masculinity which may work against the best interests of boys' (p. 92). Thus, it has a minimal influence on masculine identity unless it is reinforcing hegemonic structures.

James I's engagement with poetry is used for expressing love and admiration for his wife, which deviates from hegemonic masculine traits. Poetry, as noted by Peretz (2019), can be utilised as a method to explore and develop positive masculinity amongst men, by facilitating a healthy and open form of expression. In a later scene in Act 2, Joan insists on reading James's poem in the midst of a heated exchange. As she progresses through the verses, she realises that they are accounts of James admiring her from the window of his prison whilst she played in the court (Munro, 2016). This is a departure from the static masculine representation described by Greig and Hughes (2009), which further exemplifies James I's departure from hegemonic masculine ideals. Considering the use of poetry for expression, Joan asks James: 'Why didn't you tell me?' (Munro, 2016, p. 72), to which he replies: 'I did! I put it in a bloody poem and gave it to you!' (p. 72). Munro presents a more sentimental, emotionally mature man who seeks a closer relationship with his partner by expressing himself via his passion. This demonstrates how men benefit from subversive masculine traits and interests that develop their sense of self and relationships with others.

One of the most defining relationships for James II is his friendship with William. Against the backdrop of their childhoods was strict definitions on masculinity. When James II speaks of his father, he says: 'He was a hero. He fought eight men with a little knife. They had swords. They stabbed him fifteen times. All the wounds were on his front. He wouldn't run' (Munro, 2016, p. 119), to which William replies: 'That's a good death' (Munro, 2016, p. 119). As boys, they were taught to believe that male identity is interlinked with violence, the brutality of James I's death deemed

remarkable and heroic. Taylor, Nair and Braham (2013) suggest that, because 'masculinity develops through modeling and observation' (p. 777), this 'suggests that violent behaviors can be socially learned if adults are exposed to it during childhood and adolescence' (p. 778). In their contexts, James II and William risk following an aspirational level of violence and aggression in adherence to the culture they are brought up in.

James II and William's conformity to these hegemonized ideals does not necessitate that they are authentic to their identity.

[I]f gender is instituted through acts which are internally discontinuous, then the *appearance of substance* is precisely that, a constructed identity, a performative accomplishment which the mundane social audience, including the actors themselves, come to believe and perform in the mode of belief.

(Butler, 2004, p. 154-155: authors own emphasis)

Gender expression is developed in accordance to conventions and cues derived from social and cultural perceptions. Thus, masculine expression is imbued with an artificiality that may be removed from the innate sense of self. This is why the nature of their relationship is of note. Instead of adhering to the masculine notions of their society, James and William display an affectionate, supportive friendship for one another. Towards the end of Act 1, James finds William after he has been severely beaten by his father, Balvenie. Despite William's initial protests, '*JAMES cleans the last bit of blood off him*' (Munro, 2016, p. 139), telling him: 'Would you leave me? No. So shut up. You know what the deal is. We stand by each other. Always' (p. 139). In response, '*WILLIAM takes his hand*' (p. 139) and says: 'Always' (p. 139). This clearly establishes a strong, mutual commitment to one another, despite the competitive and confrontational nature of male relationships they have been exposed to their whole lives.

It is argued by Englar-Carlson (2006) that '[w]hen it comes to relationships, emotional boundaries seem to characterize male friendships' (p. 32), which is contra to the tender care shown between James II and William. Placing this in a 2014 context, they represent an evolution of male identity and relationships from hegemonic masculine values. Marcell *et al.* (2011, quoted in Kaplan, Rosenmann and Shuhendler, 2017) argue that 'younger cohorts maybe [sic] more open to novel

ideas and labels of masculinity' (p. 419). In showing James II and William in their childhoods and as young men, the way male identity can be informed by and reject hegemonic structures is demonstrated. Within the text, William is departing from the violent and oppressive attitudes of his family unit, being helped by James II to forge a friendship that offers security and comfort. As a reflection of contemporary Scotland, *James II* portrays youthful masculinities that subvert hegemonic masculine values. Munro depicts male identities that seek to be supportive and caring rather than competitive, emotionally restrictive and aggressive.

The gender hierarchy of hegemonic masculinity is subverted by James I. He is affectionate for his wife, Joan, expressing his love through his poetry and demanding the Scottish court show her the same respect they show him (Munro, 2016). Despite the rhetoric of his speech to the court, the respect and accommodation of his English wife is reflective of a civic nationalism that looks to accommodate many identities in Scottish nationality (Mylonas and Tudor, 2021). James I's vision for Scotland as an open-minded country, accepting one for national identity. His values are indicative of movements in contemporary Scottish politics to define Scotland as a progressive society.

With Taylor, Nair and Braham (2013) arguing that masculine identity is forged in response to one's upbringing, it would be expected that boys brought up in a ruthless, competitive court would become men that embodied the same characteristics. However, James II's friendship with William subverts this, presenting a male friendship that is emotionally intimate, caring and supportive. The media is noted for influencing attitudes and behaviours in the expression of identity (Hernandez and Macaluso, 2024), outlining the importance of Munro's work here. In challenging hegemonic masculine conventions, the writing promotes alternative, healthier forms of male friendship.

Chapter 8. Conclusion

Within the context of contemporary Scottish theatre, it is argued that Scotland's 'finest dramatists are, arguably, alive and working today' (Brown, 2019, non-paginated), with Munro's playwrighting building on ambitions to explore and reflect national identity within Scottish theatre. Munro's engagement with Scottish identity is a part of a theatre culture in Scotland that seeks to represent the multiple identities of the population (Brown, Ramage and Horvat, 2000). I argue that *The James Plays* are of particular note for the manner in which the trilogy engages with notions of masculinity, male identity and nationhood. This thesis finds that Munro uses the history play genre to reflect on contemporary Scotland, using the social, cultural and political zeitgeist of the 2014 Independence Referendum as a means to interrogate the nature of Scottish male identity.

Munro reflects on the parallels between the past and present of Scotland in saying:

We cannot know the character and thoughts of these dead kings and queens and long-gone Scots. We can speculate a whole series of possibilities from the few hard facts we can rely on, the slim historical evidence of their actions. However, I feel robustly certain that whatever their thoughts and feelings might have been, human nature is exactly the same now as it was then. Only culture and circumstances have changed.

(2016, pp. vii-viii)

Stated here is the focal point of the narrative. It is how people respond and react to circumstances that is being explored. The live debate on Scottish independence and the nature of Scottish identity in 2014 is observed through the established past of the nation. How Scotland of the 21st century engages with notions of masculinity, masculine identity and negotiations of power is represented through the medieval court of an independent Scottish kingdom. The James kings of the trilogy do not serve as complete and authentic depictions of the historical figures. Rather, they are symbolic of the Scotland Munro is writing in: a contemporary nation grappling with questions of identity and statehood.

Considering Billington's (2009) argument that history plays serve to commentate on the present, *The James Plays* demonstrate a desire to write of Scotland's past to critique her contemporary landscape. Reicher, Hopkins and Harrison (2009) find that Scottish historical figures and events are interpreted in pursuit of a particular

narrative. With a flexibility in the use of historical fact (Munro, 2022), the three plays present medieval constitutional crises that speak to the contemporary debate on independence. However, the parallel is not drawn to offer an opinion on how Scotland should vote. Written in advance of the 2014 Scottish independence referendum, *The James Plays* reflects Scotland beyond the political debate. Across the trilogy, the three Jameses navigate different constitutional crises that affect their leadership and immediate relationships. The drama of Munro's trilogy is in the personal ramifications of these seismic events, exploring how social and cultural values define identity.

A textual analysis articulates how Munro's writing depicts this complexity through the Jameses. As McKee (2003) suggests, this method facilitates a reasonable estimate in what is communicated within a text. To guide the textual analysis of *The James Plays*, four frameworks are selected, based on their detailing of masculinity, gender expression and patriarchal structures. Masculinity studies gives arguments that one's masculinity is created and moulded by social factors. This is built upon by hegemonic masculinity theory, which delineates a dominant construction of masculinity that defines the nature of authority and leadership in patriarchal systems. Patriarchy is expanded upon in feminist theory, explaining how it implements not only gender divides but gender hierarchies. Gender studies guides an understanding of how gender is expressed and understood through social conventions. Across these intersectional frameworks, the trilogy has been read to argue that the Jameses hold subversive masculinities that do not conform to the hegemonic ideals of their culture and society. In a cultural context that leans towards male-centric, patriarchal norms (Scullion, 2000), Munro's writing stands alongside other work that 'highlight[s] the distance of real men from dominant notions of hegemonic masculinity' (Reid, 2013, p.19) in Scotland.

James I and James III demonstrate that hegemonic structures will be utilised in much the same way for different ambitions. James I is less inclined towards violent outbursts and pursues authority through mandated respect, seeking to enact his political beliefs. James III is regularly aggressive and threatening, turning to intimidation to maintain the control he believes he is deserving of. His leadership is engineered for his own personal intentions. While they are markedly different

interpretations, they both exhibit hegemonic masculine characteristics in their leadership, such as competitiveness and assertiveness. In reflecting a contemporary Scotland's decisive referendum period, Munro shows that – regardless of what the intention behind the conduct is – the nation's culture and society is contingent on hegemonic structures.

The social and cultural context of an individual informs their identity, which is seen in James II and III. In showing James II in his childhood and as a young man, Munro presents the strictures of hegemonic masculinity that are imposed on males from a young age, and the impact it subsequently has on them into adulthood. James III, as a queer man, does not represent the hegemonic masculine ideal. As a consequence, he seemingly compensates for this in embodying a masculine identity that strongly adheres to hegemonic masculinity to maintain his seniority. These critique contemporary culture, highlighting the constraining nature of hegemonic ideals on masculine identity.

As is seen in the conduct of James I and II, systems that facilitate and necessitate hegemonic masculinity are challengeable. In making these subversive masculinities representative of the Scottish nation, Munro critiques the culture that facilitates these patriarchal systems and advocates for alternative values and beliefs that stand in opposition to the ideals of hegemonic structures. However, although this is accentuated in her work, it is not presented as a something to simply be overcome. Instead, Munro depicts a complex relationship between the subversive masculinities of the Jameses and the hegemonic masculine ideals they operate in relation to.

James I may be forthright in his love and admiration for his wife, but when she expresses fear and concern, and apologises for doing as such, he sees it as an inconvenience, telling her: 'Oh, you're not fucking sorry! You're sorry for yourself and that's the end of it!' (Munro, 2016, p. 70), proving verbally abusive and aggressive against her when the mood takes him. Having displayed actions that challenged the gender divide that hegemonic masculinity enacts, he is quick to belittle her when the stresses of his leadership position affect him.

James II facilitates a supportive, caring friendship with William, but kills him to maintain a balanced control of his court, reneging on his pledge to always be there for William, no matter what. Although young men are more likely to explore alternative presentations of masculine identity, 'developmental research suggests that teenagers and young adults are under social pressure to endorse traditional masculine norms, which partly mitigates over time' (Marcell *et al.*, 2011, quoted in Kaplan, Rosenmann and Shuhendler, 2017, p. 419). The intense conclusion to James II and William's friendship represents an adherence to hegemonic structures to maintain one's status. Subversive masculine traits are discarded in favour of acceptance and success.

James III comes to reject the hegemonic masculine ideals, projecting his subversive masculine identity. Butler argues:

If the ground of gender identity is the stylized repetition of acts through time, and not a seemingly seamless identity, then the possibilities of gender transformation are to be found in the arbitrary relation between such acts, in the possibility of a different sort of repeating, in the breaking or subversive repetition of that style.

(Butler, 1988, p. 520)

This is explicitly seen towards the end of the third instalment, where, '*[h]e takes off his pertinent clothing, revealing sparkling clothes beneath*' (Munro, 2016, p. 284).

Akin to drag artists, 'we see sex and gender denaturalized by means of a performance which arrows their distinctness and dramatizes the cultural mechanism of their fabricated unity' (Butler, 1999, p. 175). He gives up his leadership, creating a vacuum that his wife fills. In rejecting the status of king, so too does James III reject the ideals of hegemonic masculinity.

Despite presenting subversive masculinities, the Jameses feel compelled to infuse their identities with hegemonic masculine ideals. Butler believes that

if gender is instituted through acts which are internally discontinuous, then the *appearance of substance* is precisely that, a constructed identity, a performative accomplishment which the mundane social audience, including the actors themselves, come to believe and to perform in the mode of belief.

(1988, p. 520: author's own emphasis)

Through this, the complexity of Munro's representation is understood. Hegemonic masculinity is defined as a singular concept, but the subversion is a plurality of masculinities. James I, II and III adopt, as Butler conveys, an artificial masculine

identity to establish control and authority. But each James holds a distinct and unique identity – thus, masculinity – that is informed by and despite of the hegemonic structures they exist in. As ciphers of the people, the kings in turn reflect that Scottish nationality is complex and contradictory. Petrie (2014, non-paginated) argues: ‘Identification also carries a profound sense of personal validation’. Reiterated here is the value in interpreting the subversive masculinities of the Jameses and how these exist in relation to societal expectations for male identity and the hegemonic representation of masculinity in Scottish theatre outlined by Reid (2013). For contemporary audiences aligning themselves against a binary choice in a vote for their nation’s future, *The James Plays* show that Scottish identity is wide-encompassing, multi-layered and, ultimately, subjective.

In the aftermath of the vote, McMillan reflects that

for the time being, Scotland remains the stateless nation it was in 1982, although one utterly transformed, and infinitely more self-aware. And like every other stateless nation, it remains a rich field of dreams, where ideas about identity, belonging, past and future are always in play; a place where drama of our shared life has found an increasingly passionate and confident voice in the drama we present on stage, and where the dreaming we share in theatre plays a subtle but profound role in shaping our future, by transforming our sense of what we have been, what we are, and what we might become.

(McMillan, 2016, p. 404)

Premiering on the cusp of the referendum vote, Rona Munro took this moment of national debate to pose questions about the nature of male identity and leadership in Scotland. With Scottish history, voices and identities depicted on stage, Munro helps progress the representation of identities in Scottish theatre. She demonstrates that they are complex, interrelated and deserving of interrogation. In the ten years since the referendum vote, Munro has written three sequels to *The James Plays*. *James IV: Queen of the Fight* (2022), *Mary* (2022) and *James V: Katherine* (2024) continue her trilogy’s exploration of Scottish identity, representing ethnic, female and queer identities that subvert the hegemonic structures they exist within.

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